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RADIOCHROMIC FILM DOSIMETRY IN ANTHROPOMORPHIC PHANTOMS FOR MR GUIDED RADIOTHERAPY (MRgRT)

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Introduction

Combined use of MRI-scanners and linear accelerators provide real-time image guidance during radiotherapy (MRgRT). The presence of the MRI scanner constant magnetic field affects the response of dosimeters. Dosimetry with radiochromic films inserted in anthropomorphic phantoms, with density variations simulating those in human bodies, is used to validate dose calculations. The purpose of this study was to investigate the response change of EBT3 radiochromic films due to external magnetic fields as a function of phantom material density and gap size between phantom and film.

Materials and Methods

Three phantom materials were selected: polyurethane (PU, $\rho = 0.24 \text{ g. cm}^{-3}$), polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA, $\rho = 1.19 \text{ g. cm}^{-3}$) and polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE, $\rho = 2.2 \text{ g. cm}^{-3}$). Based on optical density measurements, detector response R and magnetic field correction factor $k_{B,M}$ were determined for 0.35 T, 0.7 T and 1.4 T magnetic field strengths, and for 0.2 mm, 0.6 mm and 0.9 mm air gap sizes at field strength 1.4 T in PMMA.

Results

Change in $R_{w,s}$ at maximum 7% for PU, 3% for PMMA and 2% for PTFE, whereas $k_{B,M}$ deviated from 1 by at maximum 1% for PMMA and

PTFE and 3% for PU. In the case of air gaps variations of 5% for $k_{B,M}$ and 7% for R were observed compared to no magnetic field present.

Conclusion

The results show significant decrease in detector response in the presence of air gaps and for lower density material. Magnetic field correction factor variation is more pronounced with the presence of magnetic field for air gaps and for lower density material.

Keywords: Radiotherapy, MRI, Detector response

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